

Supplementary Materials

Supplementary materials for: Continuous risk estimation for febrile infants when procalcitonin is unavailable: a derivation study and documented negative result

Hayden Farquhar MBBS MPHTM

Independent Researcher, Finley, New South Wales, Australia

ORCID: 0009-0002-6226-440X

This is the supplement to the retired, documented-negative-result version of this work (preprint version 2). See the Status note in the main manuscript: the prediction model does not outperform existing validated decision rules, the evidence summary is underpowered, and the pre-registered conformal analysis returned a null result. Nothing here should be used for clinical decision-making.

eTable 1. Complete 2x2 extraction data

Rule	Cohort	n	IBI	TP	FP	FN	TN	Sens	Spec	Source
Step-by-Step	Gomez 2016	2185	87	80	1114	7	984	92.0%	46.9%	Table 3–4, Fig 3
Rochester	Gomez 2016	2185	87	71	1165	16	933	81.6%	44.5%	Table 3–4
PECARN (validation)	Kuppermann 2019	838	13	13	330	0	495	100%	60.0%	eFigure 6 (IBI-specific)
PECARN (full cohort)	Kuppermann 2019	1681	30	29	635	1	1016	96.7%	61.5%	eFigure 6 (IBI-specific)
Aronson	Tsai 2021	4130	87	81	2968	6	1075	93.1%	26.6%	Abstract, cross-verified via Burstein 2024
AAP (CRP)	Umana/FIDO 2024	1821	67	66	1356	1	398	98.5%	22.7%	Table 5
BSAC	Umana/FIDO 2024	1821	67	66	1400	1	354	98.5%	20.2%	Table 5
Aronson	Umana/FIDO 2024	1821	67	60	1235	7	519	89.6%	29.6%	Table 5
NICE NG143	Umana/FIDO 2024	1821	67	62	1274	5	480	92.5%	27.4%	Table 5
Aronson 61–90d	Aronson 2025	4952	100	86	1994	14	2858	86.0%	58.9%	Abstract
Aronson 61–90d PCT	Aronson 2025	1207	27	27	404	0	776	100%	65.8%	Abstract

IBI, invasive bacterial infection; TP, true positive; FP, false positive; FN, false negative; TN, true negative.

Limitation (partial cohort overlap). The two PECARN (Kuppermann 2019) rows are not independent: the validation cohort is a subset of the full cohort, so pooling across both rows risks double-counting. The Umana/FIDO 2024 cohort spans ages up to 90 days while several rules were derived in narrower age bands. These overlaps, together with the small number of cohorts per rule (at most two), are why the main-text pooled figures are presented as a descriptive evidence summary rather than a valid pooled meta-analysis.

eTable 2. Prediction model equation

The model produces $P(\text{IBI}) = 1 / (1 + \exp(-z))$, where:

$$z = -0.058 + (-0.024 \times \text{age_days}) + (-0.097 \times \text{temp_c}) + (-0.174 \times \text{wbc}) + (0.272 \times \text{anc}) + (1.106 \times \text{ua_pos}) + (0.111 \times \text{yos_total}) + (0.256 \times \text{age_young})$$

Variable	Units	How to enter	Median (for imputation if missing)
age_days	days	Continuous, 0-60	36
temp_c	C	Continuous, rectal preferred	38.5
wbc	$\times 10^9/\text{L}$ (= $\times 10^3/\text{uL}$)	Continuous	9.9
anc	$\times 10^9/\text{L}$ (= $\times 10^3/\text{uL}$)	Continuous	3.3
ua_pos	0 or 1	1 if leukocyte esterase positive OR nitrites positive	0
yos_total	6-30	Sum of 6 YOS components (each 1-3-5)	6
age_young	0 or 1	1 if age ≤ 14 days	0

Risk tiers: very low $<0.5\%$; low 0.5-1.5%; moderate 1.5-3.0%; high $>3.0\%$.

Note. The coefficients above are from the 70/30 development-test split used for internal validation (main-text Table 2). Full complete-case-cohort coefficients are in the archived code repository (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19649953>). The equation is provided only for transparency and re-

producibility of the reported analysis; it has not been externally validated, the associated interactive tool has been withdrawn, and the model should not be used for clinical decision-making.

eTable 3. Sensitivity analyses

Age-stratified model performance

Stratum	n	IBI	Prevalence	AUC	% below 1.5%	IBI in group
Neonatal (0-28d)	1,387	51	3.7%	0.788	36.9%	3
Older (29-60d)	3,047	37	1.2%	0.739	75.7%	13
Pooled (all)	4,434	88	2.0%	0.800	—	—

Imputation method comparison

Method	AUC	% P<1%
Complete-case (no imputation during training)	0.800	—
Median imputation during training	0.769	65.1%
MICE imputation during training	0.752	55.1%

Complete-case vs imputed training comparison

	Complete cases	Incomplete cases
n	4,434	1,575
IBI rate	1.98%	0.51%
Calibration slope (complete-case model)	0.937	—
Calibration slope (imputed model)	0.718	—

eTable 4. CRP-for-PCT substitution details

Among 88 PECARN patients with both CRP and PCT results:

	CRP classification agrees	CRP classification disagrees
n	86	2
IBI in group	—	0
Nature of discordance	—	Both non-IBI; marginal threshold crossing

eTable 5. Missed IBI cases at 1% threshold

Age (days)	Temperature (C)	WBC	ANC	UA	YOS	P(IBM)	IBM type
37	39.4	5.2	2.9	Neg	8	0.98%	Meningitis
31	38.4	10.9	2.0	Neg	6	0.80%	Meningitis
57	38.3	12.8	4.1	Neg	6	0.88%	Bacteraemia

All three cases: well-appearing infants with entirely normal laboratory results. Cross-validation across 20 random splits showed a mean of 2.9 misses at the 1% threshold (range 0-4), confirming this is not an artefact of a single data split.

eTable 6. Regional recalibration framework

Predictions can be adjusted for local IBM prevalence using odds scaling:

$$\text{Adjusted odds} = \text{Original odds} \times (\text{local_prevalence} / 0.02) / ((1 - \text{local_prevalence}) / 0.98)$$

Local IBM prevalence	Adjustment factor	Approximate % classified <1%
0.5%	0.31	84%
1.0%	0.62	65%
1.5%	0.94	50%
2.0%	1.26	38%
3.0%	1.90	23%
4.0%	2.57	12%

This framework is illustrative only and was not externally validated.

eFigure 1. HSROC curves

eFigure 1. Hierarchical summary ROC curves for the PECARN rule (top) and the Aronson rule (bottom), each based on two cohorts. With only two cohorts per rule, these summaries carry little advantage over the individual source studies.

eFigure 2. Missing-input degradation

eFigure 2. Change in model AUC when each predictor is removed in turn (PCT-available subset, n=1,705). Procalcitonin removal causes the largest discrimination loss.

TRIPOD+AI checklist

Item	Section
1. Title: identify as prediction model	Title
2. Abstract: structured summary	Abstract
3a/3b. Background and objectives	Introduction
4a/4b. Source of data and study dates	Methods (Data source)
5a. Eligibility criteria	Methods (Evidence summary; Study population)
6a/6b. Outcome definition and assessment	Methods (Study population)
7a/7b. Predictors: definition and assessment	Methods (Predictor selection)
8. Sample size	Methods (Model specification and internal validation)
9. Missing data	Methods (Study population; selection-bias)
10a-10d. Statistical methods, predictor selection, model building, validation	Methods (Predictor selection; Model specification and internal validation)
11. Risk groups	Methods (Clinical risk tiers)

Item	Section
12. Development vs validation	Results; Limitations (internal validation only)
13a/13b. Flow of participants; demographics	Figure 1; Results
14a/14b. Model coefficients and performance	Table 2; Results
15a/15b. Discrimination; calibration	Results (Discrimination and calibration)
16. Interpretation	Discussion
17. Implications	Discussion (What can be retained; Conclusion)
18. Supplementary: model equation	eTable 2
19. Registration	Front matter; Methods
AI1. AI tool disclosure	Front matter (Use of AI tools)
AI2. AI in development	Methods (Software); Front matter